

MetaboLights

the home for metabolomics experiments
and derived information

EMBL-EBI Metabolomics Team

www.ebi.ac.uk

What is EMBL-EBI?

- World leading source of public biomolecular data
- Our vision is to benefit humankind by advancing scientific discovery and impact through bioinformatics.
- Part of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Europe's flagship laboratory for the life sciences.

Open Access Science

The European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI)
A New EMBL Outstation
EMBL Press Release
Heidelberg, 9 March 1993

....Its goal will be to ensure that the growing body of information from molecular biology and genome research is conveniently accessible to all facets of the European scientific and biotechnology community in ways which promote scientific progress and global competitiveness....

Today's competitive biological research and biotechnology industries are crucially dependent on up-to-date information. Modern research scientists and biotechnologists are becoming intensive users of electronic information resources - computers, software, networks and databases, and the EBI will be a European focus for the development of and access to products and services based on these technologies.

Data Sharing

- Greatly accelerates research across the life sciences
- Increases scientific reliability, reproducibility, traceability
- Enables scientists to quickly react to and build upon existing research (hypothesis generation)
- Encourages collaborations
- Increases visibility of research (citations) and impact
- Requirement of grant / publication

FAIR Guiding Principles

Provide a guideline for data producers and publishers to enhance the reusability of scientific data

www.nature.com/scientificdata

Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Re-useable

SCIENTIFIC DATA

OPEN **Comment: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship**
SUBJECT CATEGORIES
» Research data
» Publication characteristics
Mark D. Wilkinson *et al.*[#]

Good research data management is not a goal in itself, but rather the key conduit leading to knowledge discovery and innovation, and to subsequent data and knowledge integration and reuse.

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Data Management

Can metabolomics learn from the other omic techniques and not repeat many of the same mistakes that have been made in which a lot of data were collected but little information was gleaned?

Metabolomics: the final frontier?

Timothy D Veenstra ✉

Genome Medicine 2012 4:40

<https://doi.org/10.1186/qm339> | © BioMed Central Ltd. 2012

Metabolomics

metabolite

/mi'tæbəlɪt/

noun BIOCHEMISTRY

noun: **metabolite**; plural noun: **metabolites**

a substance formed in or necessary for metabolism.

Use over time for: metabolite

metabolome

/mi'tæbəlɒm/

noun BIOCHEMISTRY

noun: **metabolome**; plural noun: **metabolomes**

the total number of metabolites present within an organism, cell, or tissue.

Use over time for: metabolome

metabolomics

/mi'tæbəlɒmɪks/

noun BIOCHEMISTRY

noun: **metabolomics**

the scientific study of the set of metabolites present within an organism, cell, or tissue.

Use over time for: metabolomics

Measurement Technology

Mass spectrometry (MS) and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy are the techniques most often used for metabolome profiling

- Complex mixtures – vast range of chemical structures, properties, concentrations
- No single analysis (extraction, platform, technique) will work for all metabolites
- Selection is a compromise between sensitivity, speed, selectivity, coverage, cost

Metabolomics Applied

Agriculture
R&D

Research in agriculture including crop protection and engineering, e.g., salt and drought tolerance, plant defence

Food
Industry

Product and stress testing in food industries, e.g., water quality, control of pesticides and identification of potentially harmful bacterial strains

Health care

Medical diagnostics in healthcare, and future applications in personalised medicine, e.g., newborn screening

Metabolomic Resources

Spectral Libraries

Analysis Tools

Metabolite Knowledgebases

Repositories

Open Source Study Repository & Metabolite Knowledgebase

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights>

User Base

Submissions

Geographical distribution of submitted studies

(Top 10: China: 5115, UK: 807, USA: 803, Germany: 424, France: 194, Japan: 148, Spain: 139, India: 138, Italy: 106, Canada: 102)

MetaboLights study submission across time

Database

- Cross species, cross technique
- Comprehensive information collection
- Open access, discoverable through various portals

Reporting Standards

The Metabolomics Standards Initiative (MSI)

<http://metabolomicssociety.org/>

<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

SCIENTIFIC DATA ARTICLE IN PRESS

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/submission/>

The MetaboLights database was developed in conjunction with the metabolomics community to create a resource which aligned with community standards.

The primary requirement for a MetaboLights study submission is raw data. This is supported with rich metadata describing the samples and protocols, underpinned with controlled vocabularies / ontologies and unique identifiers. Together this represents many of the attributes of good data management as outlined in the FAIR principles.

Many funding bodies and journals require the submission of raw data to a public repository and MetaboLights is the recommended metabolomics resource for many.

It is also possible to link cross-omic data submissions through the EMBL-EBI genomics, transcriptomics and proteomics repositories.

Ontologies

Area	Ontology
Species/Organism, Organism part	National Center for Biotechnology Information Organismal Classification (NCBITAXON), World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), National Cancer Institute Thesaurus (NCIT), Environment Ontology (ENVO), Brenda Tissue and Enzyme Source Ontology (BTO)
Sample details/factors (e.g., disease state, treatment, timings)	National Cancer Institute Thesaurus (NCIT), Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO), Plant Ontology (PO), Unit of Measurement Ontology (UO), Human Phenotype Ontology (HP), Orphanet Rare Disease ontology (ORDO)
Instrumentation	Metabolomics Standards Initiative Ontology (MSIO), Chemical Methods Ontology (CHMO), Mass Spectrometry Ontology (MS), Unit of Measurement Ontology (UO) MetaboLights (MTBLS) ...
Metabolites	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (ChEBI) ... cross ref to other databases

Browse & Search

MetaboLights search bar with "breast cancer" entered. Search button. Examples: Alanine, Homo sapiens, Urine, MTBLS1. Navigation menu: Home, Browse Studies, Browse Compounds, Browse Species, Download, Help, Give us feedback, About, Submit Study, Login.

MetaboLights / Search
Filter your results
Type: compound, study
Technology
Organism
Organism Part
252 results, showing 1 to 10
Page 1 of 26
1H NMR Metabolomics Reveals Association of High Expression of Inositol 1,4,5 Trisphosphate Receptor and Metabolites in Breast Cancer Patients.
Study Identifier: MTBLS326, Organism: Homo sapiens, Study Size: 28.21MB, Study Factors: IP3R, Submitted by: aru singh ES

9-hydroxy hedychenone
COMPOUND ACCESSION: MTBLC68015
Model organisms

- [Homo sapiens \(Human\)](#)
- [Mus musculus \(Mouse\)](#)
- [Arabidopsis thaliana \(thale cress\)](#)
- [Escherichia coli](#)
- [Saccharomyces cerevisiae \(Baker's yeast\)](#)
- [Caenorhabditis elegans](#)

Areas of interest
Search areas of interest or use our model organisms links to find specific studies & compounds

Browse Studies

The screenshot shows the MetaboLights website interface. At the top, there is a search bar containing 'Homo sapiens' and a 'Search' button. Below the search bar is a navigation menu with 'Browse Studies' highlighted. On the left side, there is a 'Filter your results' panel with options for 'Type' (study selected), 'Technology', 'Organism', and 'Organism Part'. The main content area displays 145 results, showing 1 to 10. Three study entries are visible, each with a title, a table of metadata, and a 'Show more data from EMBL-EBI' button.

MetaboLights / Search

145 results, showing 1 to 10 [+ Show more data from EMBL-EBI](#)

Utilization of Metabolomics to Identify Serum Biomarkers for Hepatocellular Carcinoma in Patients with Liver Cirrhosis

Study Identifier	MTBLS17	Organism	Homo sapiens
Study Size	27.58GB	Study Factors	Disease, Injection, Experiment
Submitted by	Habtom Ressom ✉ Jinlian Wang ✉		

A lipidomic human population and translational feeding study of hepatic steatosis and de novo lipogenesis (Human plasma assay)

Study Identifier	MTBLS616	Organism	Homo sapiens
Study Size	2.45GB	Study Factors	Sampling time
Submitted by	Jules Griffin ✉		

Plasma Lipidomics for the Identification of Antecedent Memory Impairment

Study Identifier	MTBLS72	Organism	BAC:reference compound, blank, Homo sapiens
Study Size	32.22GB	Study Factors	Cognitive Status
Submitted by	Robert Padilla ✉		

Study Information

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Search

Examples: Alanine, Homo sapiens, Urine, MTBLS1

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Status Public Release Date 2019-09-19

MTBLS749: Alterations in the tyrosine and phenylalanine pathways revealed by biochemical profiling in cerebrospinal fluid of Huntington's disease subjects

Kim Kultima, Stephanie Herman

Huntington's disease (HD) is a severe neurological disease leading to psychiatric symptoms, motor impairment and cognitive decline. The disease is caused by a CAG expansion in the huntingtin (HTT) gene, but how this translates into the clinical phenotype of HD remains elusive. Using liquid chromatography mass spectrometry, we analyzed the metabolome of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from premanifest and manifest HD subjects as well as control subjects. Inter-group differences revealed that the tyrosine metabolism, including tyrosine, thyroxine, L-DOPA and dopamine, was significantly altered in manifest compared with premanifest HD. These metabolites demonstrated moderate to strong associations to measures of disease severity and symptoms. Thyroxine and dopamine also correlated with the five year risk of onset in premanifest HD subjects. The phenylalanine and the purine metabolisms were also significantly altered, but associated less to disease severity. Decreased levels of lumichrome were commonly found in mutated HTT carriers and the levels correlated with the five year risk of disease onset in premanifest carriers. These biochemical findings demonstrate that the CSF metabolome can be used to characterize molecular pathogenesis occurring in HD, which may be essential for future development of novel HD therapies.

Homo sapiens

PUBLICATIONS

Alterations in the tyrosine and phenylalanine pathways revealed by biochemical profiling i...

Herman Stephanie, Niemelä Valter, Emami Khoonsari Payam, Sun...

Descriptors Protocols Samples Assays Metabolites Files

KEYWORDS

Huntingtin (Huntington Disease) Untargeted Metabolites Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry

Factors

Phenotype : Phenotype
Replicate : Replicate
MS Format : Format

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KEYWORDS

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Factors

Phenotype : Phenotype
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Phenotype

Ontology Details

Name: EFO
Prefix: EFO
Short Form: EFO_0000651
IRI: http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/EFO_0000651

Term Details:

Definition
The Observable Form Taken By Some Character (Or Group Of Characters) In An Individual Or An Organism, Excluding Pathology And Disease. The Detectable Outward Manifestations Of A Specific Genotype.

Database Cross-reference : [SNOMEDCT:8116006](#) [NCIt:C16977](#) [MO:192](#) [NIFSTD:binlex_2087](#) [MeSH:D010641](#)

Term Editor : Tomasz Adamusiak James Malone Jie Zheng

OK

Study Information

Descriptors **Protocols** Samples Assays Metabolites Files

▣ Collapse all

Sample collection

The lumbar puncture was performed through the L3/L4 or L4/L5 interspace, and CSF was collected in a polypropylene tube that was centrifuged for 5 min at 250 x g at room temperature. The supernatant was transferred, into fresh polypropylene tubes in aliquots of 240 μ L and stored at -80 °C until analysis.

Extraction

CSF samples were thawed on ice, and 100 μ L was transferred and mixed with 410 μ L ice-cold methanol (MeOH) supplemented with an internal standard cocktail (D4-6keto-prostaglandin-F1-alpha, D4-thromboxane-B2, D4-prostaglandin-F2-alpha, D4-prostaglandin-E2, D4-prostaglandin-D2, D4-15-deoxy-delta12, 14-prostaglandin-J2, D4-cortisol and levonorgestrel) at a final concentration of 0.25 μ M. The samples were further vortexed for 15 s and incubated at -20 °C for 30 min, followed by centrifugation at 2040 [more](#)

Post Extraction Derivatization

Chromatography

The liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry analyses were performed using a Thermo Ultimate 3000 HPLC and Thermo Q-Exactive Orbitrap mass spectrometer. 10 μ L sample was injected to a Thermo Accucore aQ RP C18 column (100 x 2.1 mm, 2.6 μ m particle size). The analytical gradient was initiated with an isocratic flow for 3 min (0% B), followed by a 2.6 min gradient (0-10% B), 8.3 min (10-100% B) and 3 min (100% B), followed, finally, by re-equilibration and washing of the column for 3 min (0% B), wh [more](#)

Chromatography Instrument Column Type Column Model

Mass spectrometry

Mass spectrometry data were acquired in profile mode (in positive and negative ionization mode) on a Thermo Q-Exactive Orbitrap mass spectrometer, using a mass range of 70-900 m/z during the first 5 min and 148-900 m/z in the following 15 min (to avoid low mass contaminants) in the positive ionization mode and 70-900 m/z throughout in negative ionization mode. To improve the identification of metabolites, tandem mass spectrometry analyses in positive and negative ionization mode were performed s [more](#)

Scan Polarity Scan M/z Range Instrument Mass Analyzer Ion Source

Data transformation

The acquired raw data was converted to an open source format (mzML). Peaks were centroided by msconvert from ProteoWizard [1] and preprocessed using the following pipeline within the KNIME platform [2]: the peak-picked data was quantified by FeatureFinderMetabo [3] and the resulting features were linked across the samples using featureLinkerUnlabelledQOT [4], allowing 10 s retention time tolerance and 5 ppm mass deviation (performed irrespective of charge state across the samples). The non-default [more](#)

Metabolite identification

All metabolic features with a 75% coverage across samples were matched against an in house library of characterized metabolites using a 15 ppm mass tolerance and a 20 s time window. Metabolites (identified metabolic features) of interest were manually curated on MS/MS level when available.

Study Information

Descriptors **Protocols** Samples Assays Metabolites Files

[Collapse all](#)

Sample collection

The lumbar puncture was performed through the L3/L4 or L4/L5 interspace, and CSF was collected in a polypropylene tube that was centrifuged for 5 min at 250 x g at room temperature. The supernatant was transferred, into fresh polypropylene tubes in aliquots of 240 µL and stored at -80 °C until analysis.

Extraction

CSF samples were thawed on ice cocktail (D4-6keto-prostaglandin delta12, 14-prostaglandin-J2, D4 at -20 °C for 30 min, followed by

Post extraction Derivatization

Chromatography

The liquid chromatography-mass spectrometer. 10 µl sample was injected with an isocratic flow for 3 min (0% B) equilibration and washing of the

Chromatography Instrument Column

Mass spectrometry

Mass spectrometry data were acquired a mass range of 70-900 m/z during the first 5 min and 70-900 m/z throughout in negative ionization mode were performed

Scan Polarity Scan M/z Range

Data transformation

The acquired raw data was converted the following pipeline within the pipeline across the samples using ionization state across the samples). The non-default [more](#)

Metabolite identification

All metabolic features with a 75% coverage across samples were matched against an in house library of characterized metabolites using a 15 ppm mass tolerance and a 20 s time window. Metabolites (identified metabolic features) of interest were manually curated on MS/MS level when available.

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Post extraction Derivatization

Chromatography

The liquid chromatography-mass spectrometer. 10 µL sample was injected to a Thermo with an isocratic flow for 3 min (0% B), followed by equilibration and washing of the column for 3 min (0% B) and 70-900 m/z throughout in negative ionization mode were performed

Chromatography Instrument Column Type Column

Mass spectrometry

Mass spectrometry data were acquired in profile mode with a mass range of 70-900 m/z during the first 5 min and 70-900 m/z throughout in negative ionization mode were performed

Scan Polarity Scan M/z Range

Data transformation

The acquired raw data was converted to mzML using the following pipeline: (1) bin the # of samples using the # of state across the samples). The non-default [more](#)

Metabolite identification

All metabolic features with a 75% coverage across samples were matched against an in house library of characterized metabolites using a 15 ppm mass tolerance and a 20 s time window. Metabolites (identified metabolic features) of interest were manually curated on MS/MS level when available.

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Examples: Alanine, Homo sapiens, Urine, MTBLS1

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English 中文

Quick Start_Guide MetaboLights Account Study Description **Protocol** Sample Assay MAF Files FAQs

SECTIONS

Protocol

Protocols are central for reproducibility purposes and should provide a detailed description of the steps taken in the study. When an assay is selected, the protocol section will populate with several titled sections which you can add your specific study details to.

Eg. Liquid chromatography - Mass Spectrometry

- 1. Sample collection**
Describe the origin of samples, any relevant treatment, time points etc. and the collection and storage procedure.
- 2. Extraction**
Describe any extraction or preparation methods applied to the sample before analysis. Please also include any control samples prepared for the assay eg. pooled samples, standards, quality control, solvent blank etc
- 3. Chromatography**
Provide details of the instrument and column used (make & manufacturer), mobile phase and gradient, and settings such as temperatures, flow rate, injection volume.

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples Assays Metabolites Files

File: s_MTBLS749.txt Items per page: 494 1 - 494 of 494 < > >>

Filter

Protocol REF	Sample Name	Organism	Organism part	Phenotype	Replicate	MS format
Sample collection	1_Rep1_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format
Sample collection	1_Rep1_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format
Sample collection	1_Rep2_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format
Sample collection	1_Rep2_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format
Sample collection	10_Rep1_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format
Sample collection	10_Rep1_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format
Sample collection	10_Rep2_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format
Sample collection	10_Rep2_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format
Sample collection	11_Rep1_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format
Sample collection	11_Rep1_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format
Sample collection	11_Rep2_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format
Sample collection	11_Rep2_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols **Samples** Assays Metabolites Files

File: s_MTBL5749.txt Items per page: 494 1 - 494 of 494

Filter

Protocol REF	Sample Name	Organism	Organism part	Phenotype	Replicate	MS format																																				
Sample collection	1_Rep1_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format																																				
Sample collection	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Source Name</th> <th>Organism</th> <th>Term Source REF</th> <th>Term Accession Number</th> <th>Organism part</th> <th>Term Source REF</th> <th>Term Accession Number</th> <th>Protocol REF</th> <th>Sample Name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Uppsala, Subject 1</td> <td>Homo sapiens</td> <td>NCBITAXON</td> <td>http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/NCBITAXON/9606</td> <td>cerebrospinal fluid</td> <td>BTO</td> <td>http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BTO_0000237</td> <td>Sample collection</td> <td>1_Rep1_NEG</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Uppsala, Subject 1</td> <td>Homo sapiens</td> <td>NCBITAXON</td> <td>http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/NCBITAXON/9606</td> <td>cerebrospinal fluid</td> <td>BTO</td> <td>http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BTO_0000237</td> <td>Sample collection</td> <td>1_Rep1_POS</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Uppsala, Subject 1</td> <td>Homo sapiens</td> <td>NCBITAXON</td> <td>http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/NCBITAXON/9606</td> <td>cerebrospinal fluid</td> <td>BTO</td> <td>http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BTO_0000237</td> <td>Sample collection</td> <td>1_Rep2_NEG</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>						Source Name	Organism	Term Source REF	Term Accession Number	Organism part	Term Source REF	Term Accession Number	Protocol REF	Sample Name	Uppsala, Subject 1	Homo sapiens	NCBITAXON	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/NCBITAXON/9606	cerebrospinal fluid	BTO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BTO_0000237	Sample collection	1_Rep1_NEG	Uppsala, Subject 1	Homo sapiens	NCBITAXON	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/NCBITAXON/9606	cerebrospinal fluid	BTO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BTO_0000237	Sample collection	1_Rep1_POS	Uppsala, Subject 1	Homo sapiens	NCBITAXON	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/NCBITAXON/9606	cerebrospinal fluid	BTO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BTO_0000237	Sample collection	1_Rep2_NEG
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Uppsala, Subject 1	Homo sapiens	NCBITAXON	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/NCBITAXON/9606	cerebrospinal fluid	BTO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BTO_0000237	Sample collection	1_Rep1_POS																																		
Uppsala, Subject 1	Homo sapiens	NCBITAXON	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/NCBITAXON/9606	cerebrospinal fluid	BTO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BTO_0000237	Sample collection	1_Rep2_NEG																																		
Sample collection	10_Rep2_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format																																				
Sample collection	11_Rep1_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format																																				
Sample collection	11_Rep1_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	1	MS1 format																																				
Sample collection	11_Rep2_NEG	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format																																				
Sample collection	11_Rep2_POS	Homo sapiens	cerebrospinal fluid	control	2	MS1 format																																				

Study Information

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples **Assays** Metabolites Files

Assay Sheet 1 Assay Sheet 2 **Assay Sheet 3** Assay Sheet 4

File: a_MTBLS1987_LC-MS_positive_hilic_metabolite_profiling.txt Items per page: 69 1 - 69 of 69 << < > >>

Filter

Protocol REF	Parameter Value - Chromatography Instrument	Parameter Value - Autosampler model	Parameter Value - Column model	Parameter Value - Column type	Parameter Value - Guard column	Labeled Extract Name	Label	Protocol REF	Parameter Value - Scan polarity	Parameter Value - Scan m/z range	Parameter Value - Instrument
Chromatography	Waters ACQUITY UPLC H-Class System		ACQUITY UPLC BEH Amide (1.7 µm, 2.1 mm x 100 mm; Waters)	HILIC				Mass spectrometry	Positive	50-1000	Waters Xevo G2-S QToF
Chromatography	Waters ACQUITY UPLC H-Class System		ACQUITY UPLC BEH Amide (1.7 µm, 2.1 mm x 100 mm; Waters)	HILIC				Mass spectrometry	Positive	50-1000	Waters Xevo G2-S QToF
Chromatography	Waters ACQUITY UPLC H-Class System		ACQUITY UPLC BEH Amide (1.7 µm, 2.1 mm x 100 mm; Waters)	HILIC				Mass spectrometry	Positive	50-1000	Waters Xevo G2-S QToF

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples **Assays** Metabolites Files

Assay Sheet 1 Assay Sheet 2 **Assay Sheet 3** Assay Sheet 4

File: a_MTBLS1987_LC-MS_positive_hilic_metabolite_profiling.txt Items per page: 69 1 - 69 of 69

Filter

MS Assay Name	Raw Spectral Data File	Protocol REF	Normalization Name	Derived Spectral Data File	Protocol REF
QC_HILICpos01	HILICpos/QC_HILICpos01.raw	Data transformation		HILICpos/HILICpositive_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identificati
QC_HILICpos02	HILICpos/QC_HILICpos02.raw	Data transformation		HILICpos/HILICpositive_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identificati
QC_HILICpos03	HILICpos/QC_HILICpos03.raw	Data transformation		HILICpos/HILICpositive_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identificati

Study Information

Assays

Assay Sheet 1 **Assay Sheet 2** Assay Sheet 3 Assay Sheet 4

File: a_MTBLS1987_LC-MS_negative_reverse-phase_metabolite_profiling.txt

Items per page: 68 1 - 68 of 68

Filter

MS Assay Name	Raw Spectral Data File	Protocol REF	Normalization Name	Derived Spectral Data File	Protocol R
QC_RPLCneg01	RPLCneg/QC_RPLCneg01.raw	Data transformation		RPLCneg/RPLCnegative_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identification
QC_RPLCneg02	RPLCneg/QC_RPLCneg02.raw	Data transformation		RPLCneg/RPLCnegative_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identification
QC_RPLCneg03	RPLCneg/QC_RPLCneg03.raw	Data transformation		RPLCneg/RPLCnegative_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identification

Study Information

Assays

Assay Sheet 1 | Assay Sheet 2 | Assay Sheet 3 | Assay Sheet 4

File: a_MTBLS1987_LC-MS_negative_hilic_metabolite_profiling.txt

Items per page: 69 | 1 - 69 of 69

Filter

MS Assay Name	Raw Spectral Data File	Protocol REF	Normalization Name	Derived Spectral Data File	Protocol REF
QC_HILICneg01	HILICneg/QC_HILICneg01.raw	Data transformation		HILICneg/HILICnegative_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identification
QC_HILICneg02	HILICneg/QC_HILICneg02.raw	Data transformation		HILICneg/HILICnegative_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identification
QC_HILICneg03	HILICneg/QC_HILICneg03.raw	Data transformation		HILICneg/HILICnegative_MSMS_20eV.mgf	Metabolite identification

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples Assays Metabolites Files

MAF Sheet 1 MAF Sheet 2 MAF Sheet 3 MAF Sheet 4

File: m_MTBL1987_LC-MS_positive_hilic_metabolite_profiling_v2_maf.tsv Items per page: 10 1 – 10 of 13

Filter

Structure	Database identifier	Chemical formula	SMILES	InChI	Metabolite identification	Mass to charge	Fr
	CHEBI:26271		<chem>OC(=O)C1CCCN1</chem>	InChI=1S/C5H9NO2/c7-5(8)4-2-1-3-6-4/h4,6H,1-3H2,(H,7,8)	Proline	116.07029	
	CHEBI:17750		<chem>C[N+](C)(C)CC([O-])=O</chem>	InChI=1S/C5H11NO2/c1-6(2,3)4-5(7)8/h4H2,1-3H3	Betaine	118.08747	
	CHEBI:28300		<chem>NC(CCC(N)=O)C(O)=O</chem>	InChI=1S/C5H10N2O3/c6-3(5)9)10)1-2-4(7)8/h3H,1-2,6H2,(H2,7,8)(H,9,10)	Glutamine	147.07607	
	CHEBI:16811		<chem>CSCCC(N)C(O)=O</chem>	InChI=1S/C5H11NO2S/c1-9-3-2-4(6)5(7)8/h4H,2-3,6H2,1H3,(H,7,8)	Methionine	150.05818	

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples Assays **Metabolites** Files <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi>

MAF Sheet 1 MAF Sheet 2 MAF Sheet 3

File: m_MTBL51987_LC-MS_positive_hilic_metabolite_profiling

Filter

Structure	Database identifier
	CHEBI:26271
	CHEBI:17750
	CHEBI:28300
	CHEBI:16811

CHEBI

Home Advanced Search Browse Documentation Download Tools About CHEBI

CHEBI > Main

CHEBI:26271 - proline

Main CHEBI Ontology Automatic Xrefs Reactions Pathways Models

CHEBI Name proline
CHEBI ID CHEBI:26271
Definition An α -amino acid that is pyrrolidine bearing a carboxy substituent at position 2.
Stars ★★ This entity has been manually annotated by the CHEBI Team.
Supplier Information ChemicalBook:CB6118196, ChemicalBook:CB4149769, eMolecules:484372, MolPort-000-517-627
Download Moflix XML SDF

- Find compounds which contain this structure
- Find compounds which resemble this structure
- Take structure to the Advanced Search

Wikipedia Proline (symbol Pro or P) is an organic acid classed as a **proteogenic amino acid** (used in the biosynthesis of proteins), although it does not contain the amino group -NH₂ but is rather a secondary amine. The secondary amine nitrogen is in the protonated NH₂⁺ form under biological conditions, while the carboxyl group is in the deprotonated -COO⁻ form. The "side chain" from the α carbon connects to the nitrogen forming a pyrrolidine loop, classifying it as a **cyclic amino acid**. It is non-essential in humans, meaning the body can synthesize it from the non-essential amino acid L-glutamate. It is encoded by all the codons starting with CC (CCU, CCC, CCA, and CCG). Proline is the only nonproteogenic **secondary amino acid** which is a secondary amine, as the nitrogen atom is attached both to the α -carbon and to a chain of three carbons that together form a five-membered ring.

Formula C₅H₉NO₂
Net Charge 0
Average Mass 115.13050
Monoisotopic Mass 115.06333
InChI InChI=1S/C5H9NO2/c7-5(8)4-2-1-3-6-4/r4,6H,1-3H2,(1,7,8)
InChIKey ONBBWKKTOPOVA-UHFFFAOYSA-N
SMILES OC(=O)C1CCCN1

Metabolite of Species **Details**
Daphnia magna (NCBI:tax35525) See: Mixtures of similarly acting compounds in Daphnia magna: From gene to metabolite and beyondTine Vandenbrouck, Oliver A.H. Jones, Nathalie Dom, Julian L. Griffin, Wim De CoenEnvironment International 36 (2010) 254-268

Roles Classification
Bronsted base
A molecular entity capable of accepting a hydron from a donor (Bronsted acid).

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples Assays **Metabolites** Files <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi>

MAF Sheet 1 MAF Sheet 2 MAF Sheet 3

File: m_MTBL51987_LC-MS_positive_hilic_metabolite_profiling

Filter

Structure	Database identifier
	CHEBI:26271
	CHEBI:17750
	CHEBI:28300
	CHEBI:16811

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CHEBI:26271 - proline

Main CHEBI Ontology Automatic Xrefs Reactions Pathways Models

CHEBI Name proline
CHEBI ID CHEBI:26271
Definition An α -amino acid that is pyrrolidine bearing a carboxy substituent at position 2.
Stars ★★☆☆ This entity has been manually annotated by the CHEBI Team.
Supplier Information ChemicalBook:CB6118196, ChemicalBook:CB4149769, eMolecules:484372, MolPort-000-517-627
Download Moflix XML SDF

- Find compounds which contain this structure
- Find compounds which resemble this structure
- Take structure to the Advanced Search

Wikipedia License

Proline (symbol Pro or P) is an organic acid classed as a **proteogenic amino acid** (used in the biosynthesis of proteins), although it does not contain the amino group -NH₂ but is rather a secondary amine. The secondary amine nitrogen is in the protonated NH₂⁺ form under biological conditions, while the carboxyl group is in the deprotonated -COO⁻ form. The "side chain" from the α carbon connects to the nitrogen forming a pyrrolidine loop, classifying it as a **cyclic amino acid**. It is non-essential in humans, meaning the body can synthesize it from the non-essential amino acid L-glutamate. It is encoded by all the codons starting with CC (CCU, CCC, CCA, and CCG). Proline is the only proteogenic **secondary amino acid** which is a secondary amine, as the nitrogen atom is attached both to the α -carbon and to a chain of three carbons that together form a five-membered ring.

Read full article at Wikipedia

Formula C₅H₉NO₂
Net Charge 0
Average Mass 115.13050
Monoisotopic Mass 115.06333
InChI InChI=1S/C5H9NO2/c7-5(8)4-2-1-3-4/t4,6H,1-3H2,(1,7,8)
InChIKey ONBBWKKTOPOVGA-UHFFFAOYSA-N
SMILES OC(=O)C1CCCN1

Metabolite of Species Details

Daphnia magna (NCBI:tax35525)
See: Mixtures of similarly acting compounds in Daphnia magna: From gene to metabolite and beyondTine Vandenbrouck, Oliver A.H. Jones, Nathalie Dom, Julian L. Griffin, Wim De CoenEnvironment International 36 (2010) 254-268

Roles Classification Details

Bronsted base
A molecular entity capable of accepting a hydron from a donor (Bronsted acid).

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples Assays Metabolites Files

MAF Sheet 1 MAF Sheet 2 MAF Sheet 3 MAF Sheet 4

File: m_MTBL1987_LC-MS_positive_hilic_metabolite_profiling_v2_maf.tsv Items per page: 10 1 – 10 of 13

Filter

Structure	Database identifier	Chemical formula	SMILES	InChI	Metabolite identification	Mass to charge	Fr
	CHEBI:26271		<chem>OC(=O)C1CCCN1</chem>	InChI=1S/C5H9NO2/c7-5(8)4-2-1-3-6-4/h4,6H,1-3H2,(H,7,8)	Proline	116.07029	
	CHEBI:17750		<chem>C[N+](C)(C)CC([O-])=O</chem>	InChI=1S/C5H11NO2/c1-6(2,3)4-5(7)8/h4H2,1-3H3	Betaine	118.08747	
	CHEBI:28300		<chem>NC(CCC(N)=O)C(O)=O</chem>	InChI=1S/C5H10N2O3/c6-3(5(9)10)1-2-4(7)8/h3H,1-2,6H2,(H2,7,8)(H,9,10)	Glutamine	147.07607	
	CHEBI:16811		<chem>CSCCC(N)C(O)=O</chem>	InChI=1S/C5H11NO2S/c1-9-3-2-4(6)5(7)8/h4H,2-3,6H2,1H3,(H,7,8)	Methionine	150.05818	

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples Assays **Metabolites** Files

MAF Sheet 1 MAF Sheet 2 MAF Sheet 3 MAF Sheet 4

File: m_MTBLS1987_LC-MS_positive_reverse-phase_metabolite_profiling_v2_maf.tsv

Items per page: 18 1 - 18 of 18

Filter

Structure	QC Cpos07	QC RPLCpos08	QC RPLCpos09	Woman HCW099 RPLCpos	Woman Pt019 RPLCpos	Woman Pt119 RPLCpos	Men Pt074 RPLCpos	Woman Pt022 RPLCpos	Men Pt010 RPLCpos
Structure not available	1889097	5.308643602	5.339502163	5.609366786	5.00663743	4.679825794	5.33411991	4.604604231	5.169805
	1811223	3.267285197	3.271734835	3.461711921	3.424440921	3.424736856	3.348127133	3.467831182	3.369563
	022534	4.545411209	4.535673448	4.778082405	4.957507954	4.912036478	4.890949777	4.694373625	4.802197
	1670279	2.929480823	2.802480293	3.436838655	2.919315525	3.004794026	2.759335266	3.009196088	3.024872

Study Information

Descriptores Protocols Samples Assays Metabolites **Files**

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ISA METADATA Download

search meta data

<input type="checkbox"/>			

RAW / DERIVED FILES

search raw files

Study Information

Descriptors Protocols Samples Assays Metabolites **Files**

FTP Download Aspera Download Help

ISA METADATA

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
33	Investigation Person Roles Term Source REF										
34	STUDY										
35	Study Identifier	MTBLS1987									
36	Study Title	Kynurenic acid underlies sex-specific immune responses to COVID-19									
37	Study Description	Sex-related differences in Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) severity and mortality exist, with the male sex being a potential risk factor									
38	Study Submission Date										
39	Study Public Release Date	08/09/2020									
40	Study File Name	s_MTBLS1987.txt									
41	STUDY DESIGN DESCRIPTORS										
42	Study Design Type	COVID-19	Immune re ultra-perfo untargeted metabolites								
43	Study Design Type Term Accession Number	http://purl.obo.org/http://www.http://purl/http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/ontology/MTBLS_000279									
44	Study Design Type Term Source REF	DOID	MTBLS	CHMO	MTBLS						
45	STUDY PUBLICATIONS										
46	Study PubMed ID										
47	Study Publication DOI	10.1101/2020.09.06.20189159									
48	Study Publication Author List	Yuping Cai, Daniel J. Kim, David I. Broadhurst, Takehiro Takahashi, Armau Casanova-Massana, Akiko Iwasaki, Caroline H. Johnson, Yanyan Cai, Daniel J. Kim, David I. Broadhurst, Takehiro Takahashi, Armau Casanova-Massana, Akiko Iwasaki, Caroline H. Johnson, Yanyan Cai									
49	Study Publication Title	Sex-specific metabolites associated with immune responses for COVID-19 disease									
50	Study Publication Status	Published									
51	Study Publication Status Term Accession Number	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/EFO_0001796									
52	Study Publication Status Term Source REF	EFO									
53	STUDY FACTORS										
54	Study Factor Name	Gender	Disease	Drug treatr	Nasophary	Oropharyngeal	swabs	load			
55	Study Factor Type	Gender	disease	drug	nasophary	oropharyngeal	swabs	load			
56	Study Factor Type Term Accession Number	http://purl.obo.org/http://purl/http://purl/http://www.http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/ontology/placeholder									
57	Study Factor Type Term Source REF	NCIT	DOID	CHEBI	MTBLS	MTBLS					
58	STUDY ASSAYS										
59	Study Assay File Name	a_MTBLS1987_a_MTBLS11_a_MTBLS11_a_MTBLS1987_IC-MS_positive_reverse-phase_metabolite_profiling.txt									
60	Study Assay Measurement Type	metabolite pr: metabolite metabolite metabolite profiling									
61	Study Assay Measurement Type Term Accession Number	http://purl.obo.org/http://purl/http://purl/http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000366									
62	Study Assay Measurement Type Term Source REF	OBI	OBI	OBI	OBI						

MetaboLights submissions are powered by the ISA software suite. so experimental data gets submitted in ISA-Tab format. The Investigation/Study/Assay (ISA) infrastructure is the first general-purpose format and freely available desktop software suite targeted to experimentalists, curators and developers and that assists in the reporting and local management of experimental metadata (i.e. sample characteristics, technology and measurement types, sample-to-data relationships) from studies employing one or a combination of technologies.

Study Information

Descriptores Protocols Samples Assays Metabolites **Files**

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ISA METADATA Download

search meta data

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	a_MTBL1987_LC-MS_negative_hilic_metabolite_profiling.txt	September 08 2020 08:33:26	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	a_MTBL1987_LC-MS_negative_reverse-phase_metabolite_profiling.txt	September 08 2020 08:32:52	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	a_MTBL1987_LC-MS_positive_hilic_metabolite_profiling.txt	September 08 2020 08:39:47	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	a_MTBL1987_LC-MS...		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	i_Investigation.txt	September 07 2020 15:54:36	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	m_MTBL1987_LC-M...		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	m_MTBL1987_LC-M...		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	m_MTBL1987_LC-M...		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	m_MTBL1987_LC-M...		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	s_MTBL1987.txt		

RAW / DERIVED FILES

search raw files

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	HILICneg	September 07 2020 15:54:36	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	HILICpos	September 07 2020 15:53:13	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	RPLCneg	September 16 2020 22:14:29	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	men_HCW011_RPLCneg.raw		Download
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<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	men_HCW036_RPLCneg.raw		Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	men_HCW059_RPLCneg.raw		Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	men_HCW067_RPLCneg.raw		Download

RAW / DERIVED FILES

search raw files

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	HILICneg	September 07 2020 15:54:36	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	HILICpos	September 07 2020 15:53:13	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	RPLCneg	September 16 2020 22:14:29	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	RPLCpos	September 07 2020 16:33:31	Download

Mentimeter code 1504 3132
(www.menti.com)

(squeak)

Mentimeter code 5122 7641
(www.menti.com)

(MTBLS2014)

Studies with Vitis

3821 samples

16,682 metabolites

184 Gb

vitis labrusca (#2)

vitis vinifera (#25)

Vitis (#29)

vitis rotundifolia (#2)

number of studies in MetaboLights – Oct 2021 (prep to public)

Study Submission

Individual researcher

Labs
Phenome Centers

Industry
Metabolon etc

Online
guided
submission

Pipeline
Template

REST
API - Access

Online
Editor

SUBMITTED

CURATION

REVIEW

PUBLIC

Quickstart Guide

<p>Create account</p>		<p>To submit a study, first create an account with MetaboLights www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/login</p>
<p>Create new study</p>		<p>Select Submit study to create a new study. Create online: step by step guide, recommended option for submission. API option also available. NB. the unique accession number assigned to your study MTBLS... will be the final reference, please use this in manuscripts. <i>NB. For journal editor reviewer link see information below.</i></p>
<p>Edit study online</p>		<p>If you don't have all the information available when creating your study, don't worry. Once the initial study has been created you can use the online editor option to add, edit and upload data. Access through your My Studies page.</p>
<p>Study curation process</p>		<p>Once the validation criteria has been met, change 'Status' to move study into the curation queue. NB. this process can take at least 4 weeks.</p>
<p>Private study link available for reviewers</p>		<p>Following completion of the curation process the status will be updated to review and a private link to your study will be available for you to share with journal editors etc.</p>
<p>Study publication</p>		<p>Curated studies will become public once the date you have set is reached. You can update this at any stage by contacting us directly metabolights-help@ebi.ac.uk</p>

Online Study Submission

Please see tutorial video for details – <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/help>

My studies Logout

Create Study Upload files Study description Sample & assay details

MetaboLights - Create new study

Your MetaboLights study
Your study has been assigned the unique identifier [MTBLS_DEV2389](#)
Please refer to this identifier in any communication with the MetaboLights team.

How to reference your MetaboLights study
Please use MTBLS_DEV2389 when referencing this study in manuscripts etc.
together with the URL www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/MTBLS_DEV2389

Please also cite the following MetaboLights paper
Haug et al. MetaboLights-- an open-access general-purpose repository for metabolomics studies and associated meta-data. Nucl. Acids Res. (2013) doi: 10.1093/nar/gks1004

The above information will also be sent to you by email.

Next

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/presubmit>

Online Study Submission

What to include in a study?

In the first section of the presentation you can see examples of the information found in MetaboLights studies.

The **Guided submission** will take you through the required information step-by-step. It will guide you through raw and sample data upload, creating assays and provide you with controlled vocabulary/ontology options in relevant fields.

If you don't have all the information to hand, don't worry! You can access and edit your study at anytime from your My Studies page, including adding samples, extra assays, data and much more.

MetaboLights APIs

- Also available for Institutional submissions
- API access to all parts of the study

POST /metabolights/swagger/ws/partners/metabolon/{study_id}/confirm Confirm all files are uploaded

Implementation Notes
Confirm that all raw/mzML files has been uploaded to this studies upload folder.
Files uploaded for clients will be added to the final study before templates are applied
This may take some time as mzML validation and conversion to ISA-Tab will now take place

Parameters

Parameter	Value	Description	Parameter Type	Data Type
study_id	<input type="text" value="(required)"/>	MTBLS Identifier	path	string
user_token	<input type="text" value="(required)"/>	User API token	header	string

Error Status Codes

HTTP Status Code	Reason
200	OK.
400	Bad Request. Server could not understand the request due to malformed syntax.
401	Unauthorized. Access to the resource requires user authentication.
403	Forbidden. Access to the study is not allowed for this user.
404	Not found. The requested identifier is not valid or does not exist.
417	Unexpected result.

[Try it out!](#)

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/ws/api/spec.html#!/spec/about>

My Studies

Once created a study will appear in your 'My studies' page

The screenshot displays the 'My Studies' page in the MetaboLights Study Editor. The page has a blue header with the MetaboLights logo and the text 'MetaboLights Study Editor'. On the right side of the header, there are links for 'My studies' and 'Logout'. Below the header, the main content area is titled 'My Studies' and includes a search bar and a 'Video tutorial' link. A red box highlights the filter tabs: 'All', 'Submitted', 'In Curation', 'In Review', and 'Public'. Below the filters, there are two study entries:

- MTBLS83: Insert title here - Title should be identical to publication title**
Status: Submitted (yellow tag) | Release Date: 2020-04-30
SUMMARY: Insert information here such as publication abstract
Buttons: Guided submission, Study overview
- MTBLS84: MTBLS83: Insert title here -**
Status: Submitted (yellow tag) | Release Date: 2020-04-30
SUMMARY: Insert information here such as publication abstract
Buttons: Guided submission, Study overview

A 'Feedback' button is visible on the right side of the page.

My Studies

From here you can edit and update using the guided submission or study overview options

The image shows a screenshot of the MetaboLights Study Editor interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the MetaboLights logo, the text "MetaboLights Study Editor", and navigation links for "My studies" and "Logout". Below the header, there is a search bar and a list of studies. Two study entries are visible, both with the title "MTBLS83: Insert title here - Title should be identical to publication title". The first study has a status of "Submitted" and a release date of "2020-04-30". The second study has a status of "Submitted" and a release date of "2023-04-30". Both study entries have buttons for "Guided submission" and "Study overview". A red box highlights these buttons in the first study entry. A red arrow points from this box to a callout window titled "MetaboLights - Guided submission". This callout window contains the following text: "The following steps will guide you through creating your metabolomics study. Once submitted you can view and edit your study through the MetaboLights website." Below this text, there are two buttons: "Guided submission" and "Switch to study overview". At the bottom of the callout window, there is a green button that says "> Let's get started". To the right of the callout window, there are two overlapping screenshots of the MetaboLights website. The top screenshot shows the main page with the title "Analysis of the human adult urinary metabolites variations with age, body mass index and gender by implementing a comprehensive workflow for untargeted and OPLS statistical analysis" and a "Feedback" button. The bottom screenshot shows a detailed view of a study, including a title, abstract, and a list of authors.

Study Completion

The publication of your study is in your control, however there are some factors to remember!

Validation **Failed**

You must ensure your study passes all the required validations. If the study displays **'Failed'**, please look at the study validations tab to find out more.

All **'Errors'** must be addressed to progress the study. **'Warning'** can help to alert you to missing or mismatched information.

The validation box will disappear when all validations are successful.

The screenshot shows the MetaboLights interface for a study titled "A metabolomic study of urinary changes in type 2 diabetes in human compared to the control group". The study status is "Failed". The "Study Validations" tab is active, showing a list of errors and warnings. A red box highlights the "Errors" section, and a yellow box highlights the "Warnings" section. A green box highlights the "Basic" section, and a blue box highlights the "Assays" section. A red box highlights the "Errors" section at the bottom of the page.

Errors

Warning

Info

Success

All

Basic

Successfully read the investigation file

Successfully read the study section of the investigation file

Successfully found the reference to the sample sheet filename

Successfully found one or more samples

Successfully found one or more assays

Successfully found one or more factors

Successfully found one or more descriptors

publication

Found a publication

Assays

Empty file found in a sub-directory

Assay sheet "h_MTB_S92_LC-MS_negative_XMS_metabolite_profiling.txt" column "Extract Name" is empty

Errors

Warning

Info

Success

All

Could not find any study design descriptors

Study Completion

The publication of your study is in your control, however there are some factors to remember!

Validation **Failed**

Release Date **2019-01-09**

Before progressing your study, give an approximate date when you would like the data to be publicly accessible.

*The curation process requires a minimum of 4 weeks so you will not be able to set this earlier than 4 weeks in the future.

*Once in curation/review stage, you can change this date at any time by contacting us directly
metabolights-help@ebi.ac.uk

Study Completion

The publication of your study is in your control, however there are some factors to remember!

Validation **Failed**

Release Date 2019-01-09

Status Submitted

MetaboLights is an open-access general-purpose repository for metabolomics studies and associated meta-data.

MetaboLights (http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights) is the first general-purpose, open-access repository for metabolomics studies, their raw experimental data and associated metadata, maintained by one of the major open-access data providers in molecular biology. Metabolomic profiling is an important tool for research into biological functioning and for the systemic perturbations caused by diseases, diet and the environment. The effectiveness of such methods depends on the availability of public open data across a broad range of experimental methods and conditions. The MetaboLights repository, powered by the open source ISA framework, is cross-species and cross-techniques and will cover metabolite structures and their reference spectra as well as their biological roles, locations, concentrations and raw data from metabolic experiments. Studies automatically receive a stable unique accession number that can be used as a publication reference (e.g. MBL012). At present, the repository includes 15 submitted studies, encompassing 93 protocols for 714 assays, and span over 8 different species including human, *Caenorhabditis elegans*, *Mus musculus* and *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Eight studies have been published in CHEBI. These studies cover a variety of techniques, including NMR spectroscopy.

Accessibility: Your study is private. Only the study submitters are able to view and make changes to the study.

What's next?
Once you have completed your study and it has met the validation criteria, you can click your study passes the validation checks (see the validation tab in your study). Once you have completed your study and it has met the validation criteria, you can click your study passes the validation checks (see the validation tab in your study). Once you have completed your study and it has met the validation criteria, you can click your study passes the validation checks (see the validation tab in your study).

Submitted
In Curation

Are you sure?
Confirm Back

To progress you will need to change the study status to let us know it is ready!

This can only be done once the validations are successful.

Status **In Curation**

Success!

There are validation errors. Fix any problems before attempting to change study status.

OK

Check validations

Browse Compounds

MetaboLights

Homo sapiens Search

Examples: Alanine, Homo sapiens, Urine, MTBLS1

Home Browse Studies **Browse Compounds** Browse Species Download Help Give us feedback About Submit Study Login

MetaboLights / Search

Filter your results

Type

- compound

Compound features

- Species
- Pathways
- Reactions
- NMR
- MS

Technology

Organism

Organism Part

3149 results, showing 1 to 10

Show more data from EMBL-EBI

hyaluronic acid

COMPOUND ACCESSION
MTBLC16336

Identified in CHEBI:16336

lysophosphatidylcholine 18:2

COMPOUND ACCESSION
MTBLC64549

DESCRIPTION
A lysophosphatidylcholine in which the acyl group (position not specified) contains 18 carbons and 2 double bonds.

Identified in CHEBI:64549, MTBLS4

methylene group

COMPOUND ACCESSION
MTBLS1

Compound: Chemistry

MetaboLights / Compound page

2D 3D

MOL SMILES InChIkey

MTBLC15345: Acetoacetyl-CoA

Export Upload Reference Spectra Help

Chemistry Biology Pathways Reaction Literature

Compound Description
A 3-oxoacyl-CoA that results from the formal condensation of the thiol group of coenzyme A with the carboxy group of acetoacetic acid.

Identification

IUPAC Names	S-acetoacetyl-coenzyme A
Molecular Formula	C25H40N7O18P3S
Mass	851.60876
Monoisotopic Mass	851.136
Charge	0
InChI	InChI=1S/C25H40N7O18P3S/c1-13(33)8-16(35)54-7-6-27-15(34)4-5-28-23(38)20(37)25(2,3)10-47-53(44,45)50-52(42,43)46-9-14-19(48-51(39,40)41)18(36)24(48-14)32-12-31-17-21(26)29-11-30-22(17)32/h11-12,14,18-20,24,36-37H,4-10H2,1-3H3,(H,27,34)(H,28,38)(H,42,43)(H,44,45)(H2,26,29,30)(H2,39,40,41)/t14-,18-,19-,20+,24-/m1/s1
InChIKey	OJFDKHTZOUZBOS-CITAKDKDSA-N
SMILES	CC(=O)CC(=O)SCCNC(=O)CCNC(=O)[C@H](O)C(C)(C)COP(O)(=O)OP(O)(=O)OC[C@H]1O[C@H]([C@H](O)[C@H]1O)P(O)(O)=O)n1cnc2cNnnc12
Synonyms	3-Acetoacetyl-CoA Acetoacetyl Coenzyme A Acetoacetyl-CoA

Compound: Biology

MetaboLights / Compound page

2D 3D

MOL SMILES InChIKey

MTBLC15345: Acetoacetyl-CoA

Export Upload Reference Spectra Help

Chemistry **Biology** Pathways Reaction Literature

Species

<i>Mus musculus</i>	NCBI:10090 19425150 MTBLS173 MTBLS225 MTBLS225 MTBLS225
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NCBI:562 21988631

Compound: Pathways

MetaboLights / Compound page

2D 3D

MOL SMILES InChIKey

MTBLC15345: Acetoacetyl-CoA

Export Upload Reference Spectra Help

Chemistry Biology **Pathways** Reaction Literature

WikiPathways KEGG Pathways Reactome Pathways

Select Species
Homo sapiens

Select Pathways
Mitochondrial Fatty Acid Beta-Oxidation

+

RESET

-

Compound: Pathways

MetaboLights / Compound page

2D 3D

MOL SMILES InChIKey

MTBLC15345: Acetoacetyl-CoA

Export Upload Reference Spectra Help

Chemistry Biology Pathways Reaction Literature

WikiPathways KEGG Pathways Reactome Pathways

Fatty acid degradation

Wikipedia: Citrate cycle

Wikipedia: Citrate cycle

Compound: Pathways

MetaboLights / Compound page

2D 3D

MOL SMILES InChIKey

MTBLC15345: Acetoacetyl-CoA

Export Upload Reference Spectra Help

Chemistry Biology **Pathways** Reaction Literature

WikiPathways KEGG Pathways **Reactome Pathways**

Select Species
Homo sapiens

Select Pathways
Cholesterol biosynthesis

Search for a term, e.g. pen ...

Cholesterol biosynthesis via lathosterol

Cholesterol biosynthesis via lanosterol

TXN - 0 entities flagged Interactors: Exclude reactome

Compound: Reactions

MetaboLights / Compound page

2D 3D

MTBLC15345: Acetoacetyl-CoA

Export Upload Reference Spectra Help

Chemistry Biology Pathways **Reaction** Literature

Select Reaction

2 acetyl-CoA = acetoacetyl-CoA + CoA

Source: Rhea: 21036

2 acetyl-CoA acetoacetyl-CoA CoA

MOL SMILES InChIKey

Compound: Literature

The screenshot displays the MetaboLights interface for the compound MTBLC15345: Acetoacetyl-CoA. At the top, a navigation bar includes links for Home, Browse Studies, Browse Compounds, Browse Species, Download, Help, Give us feedback, About, Submit Study, and Login. Below this, the breadcrumb path is MetaboLights / Compound page. On the left, there are tabs for 2D and 3D views, with 2D selected. A chemical structure of Acetoacetyl-CoA is shown, along with a search icon and buttons for MOL, SMILES, and InChIKey. The main content area features a dark header with the compound name and options to Export, Upload Reference Spectra, and Help. A navigation bar below the header includes links for Chemistry, Biology, Pathways, Reaction, and Literature (which is highlighted). Under the Literature tab, the section is titled "Europe PubMed Central results" and lists five abstracts:

- Identification, purification and characterization of an acetoacetyl-CoA thiolase from rat liver peroxisomes.
- Metabolism of acetyl-CoA by isolated peroxisomal fractions: formation of acetate and acetoacetyl-CoA.
- Feasibility study to assess the impact of a lifestyle intervention ('LivingWELL') in people having an assessment of their family history of colorectal or breast cancer.
- Interrelationships between 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA synthase, acetoacetyl-CoA and ketogenesis.
- Acetoacetate utilization by human placental mitochondria.

Metabolite Knowledgebases

Counterpart Repositories

- MetaboLights (MTBLSxxx)
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights>
ISA-TAB – ‘i_Investigation.txt’, ‘s_MTBLS*.txt’ ...
- Metabolomics Workbench (STxxx)
<https://www.metabolomicsworkbench.org>
mwTAB
- MetaboBank (MTBKSxxx)
<https://mb2.ddbj.nig.ac.jp>
MAGE-TAB – IDF + SDRF
- GNPS/MassIVE (MSVxxx)
<https://massive.ucsd.edu/ProteoSAFe>
‘params.xml’ + ‘gnps_metadata.tsv’ (ReDU)

The screenshot displays the MetaboLights website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the text 'Center for Computational Mass Spectrometry' and a search bar. Below this, the 'MetaboBank' section is visible, featuring a search bar and a 'Submission' button. The main content area is titled 'METABOLOMICS WORKBENCH' and includes a search bar and a 'Log in / Register' link. The 'MetaboLights' section is also present, with a search bar and a 'Submit to MetaboLights' button. The interface is clean and professional, with a blue and white color scheme.

Browse & Search (some more)

The screenshot displays the MetabolomeXchange website interface. At the top, the URL *metabolomexchange.org* is shown in green, along with a notification that 1513 datasets are available. The main heading "MetabolomeXchange" is prominently displayed in orange and green, with the tagline "An international data aggregation and notification service for metabolomics." below it.

The search results section shows a search for "149881 Results". The left sidebar lists various categories: Transcripts (149881), Genomics (12279), Proteomics (9352), Metabolomics (1581), Multiomics (4057), Models (8418), and Unknown (12634). The main content area displays two search results. The first result is titled "Bulk RNA Barcoding and sequencing (BRB-seq) protocol for RNA-seq of human pre-adipocytes and differentiated adipocytes" and includes details such as "ORGANISM(S): Homo sapiens", "2018-02-06 | E-MTAB-6469 | ArrayExpress", and a link to "RNA-seq of coding RNA". The second result is titled "Transcription profiling by array of oral squamous cell cancer (OSCC) surgical margins defined by narrow band imaging." and includes the text "The purpose of this study was to provide molecular evidence that surgical margin definition using na..." and the website "www.omicsdi.org".

Multi-omics

BioImage Archive

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive>

 COVID-19 Data Portal

Hologenomics for sustainable food production 2019-2022

MetaboLights

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights>

 BioStudies.

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies>

BioSamples

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples>

European Nucleotide Archive

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>

MGNify

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics>

PRIDE

PRoteomics IDentifications Database

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride>

HoloFood Data Portal

<https://www.holofooddata.org>

MGNify

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics>

- Histology
- Targeted metabolites
- Inflammatory markers

- Host genome
- Host transcriptome

- Metatranscriptome
- Metagenome

- Non-targeted metabolites

HoloFood Data Portal

<https://www.holofooddata.org>

- *Histology*
- *Targeted metabolites*
- *Inflammatory markers*

- *Host genome*
- *Host transcriptome*

- *Metatranscriptome*
- *Metagenome*

- *Non-targeted metabolites*

MGNify

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics>

Home > Samples Related: Animals

Filter samples

Animal system

chicken

Sample type

inflammatory_markers

Accession contains

Title contains

Treatment Search

E.g. algae 2.0% "Day 60"

probio 21

Animal accession starts with

See the list of animals for details

Ordering

Apply

Samples

Samples listed are extraction-level BioSamples, derived from animals across HoloFood trials.

Download all as TSV

Sample accession Animal

SAMEA112906891 SAMEA112

SAMEA112906892 SAMEA112

SAMEA112906895 SAMEA112

Home > Samples > SAMEA01

Related: Animal SAME001

SAMEA01: chicken caecum extraction

Sample data for SAMEA01, a HoloFood metagenomic chicken sample

Sample details

Sample metadata

Metagenomics

Home > Animals > SAMEA112905388

SAMEA112905388:

System

chicken

Samples

View 8 derived samples

API endpoint

</api/animals/SAMEA112905388>

Animal metadata

Metadata for sample SAMEA112905388, stored in BioSamples.

Sample SAMEA01 has metagenomic datasets available on MGNify. View sample on MGNify

Analyses

Analysis accession	Run accession	MGNify pipeline version	Experiment type	Detail
MGYA00606210	ERR4918394	5.0	metagenomic	View on MGNify

[inflammatory-markers](#) [View](#)

[inflammatory-markers](#) [View](#)

FindingPheno

MetaboLights in Galaxy

“Standardised metabolite annotation workflows for enhancing biological interpretation in metabolomic data repositories”

The image displays two screenshots of the Galaxy MetaboLights Labs interface. The left screenshot shows the 'Welcome to the MetaboLights Labs Galaxy Instance!' page, which includes a search bar, navigation links for 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Admin', 'Help', 'User', and 'Using 212.3 GB'. A sidebar on the left lists various tools and workflows, with 'WORKFLOWS' selected. The main content area features the MetaboLights logo and a welcome message. Below the welcome message are logos for 'isaAPI' and 'Wm' (Wellcome Genome Campus), along with the URL <https://metabolights-labs.org>. The right screenshot shows a workflow editor for 'Metabolights DB - XCMS - BeamSpy Workflow'. The workflow consists of several steps: '1. XCMS - Compound file', '2. MetaboLights DB - Annotation', '3. BeamSpy Workflow', and '4. Summary Report'. The workflow is visualized as a series of interconnected boxes representing different tools and data processing steps.

Rick Dunn (PI), Tim Ebbels (PI), Claire O'Donovan (PI)

MARIANA-2

“Linking mass spectrometry computational ecosystems to enhance biological insights of publicly-available data”

GNPS LCMS Dashboard - Version 0.57 Documentation GNPS Datasets Select Other Dataset Files

Data Selection [Show/Hide](#)

File Selection [Upload File](#)

GNPS USI:

USI View Selection:

GNPS USI2:

[Copy URL, Link to the Visualization](#) [Copy Short Temporary URL](#)

Molecular Network 1 Files at GNPS

Comment:

LCMS Viewer Options

Show MS2 Markers:

Show USI2 LCMS Map:

Show Filters:

Show Overlay:

Feature Finding:

XIC Options [Advanced XIC Options](#)

XIC m/z: XIC Formula:

XIC Tolerance (Da): XIC Tolerance (ppm): XIC Tolerance Unit:

XIC Retention Time View/Integration Limits:

XIC Integration: XIC Normalization: XIC Grouping:

MS2 Options

MS2 Identifier:

TIC Options

TIC option: Show Multiple TICs:

Rendering Options Dark Mode

SVG:

Advanced Panels

Visualization Options Import Options Replay Options

[Sync Options](#) [Sync Isolate \(Followed\)](#) [Sync Terminate \(Followed\)](#)

[Replay Advance](#) [Replay Rewind](#)

Outreach & Training

PUBLIC AWARENESS

PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT

WORKSHOPS AT INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

ASMS 2023 Annual Conference

19th Annual Conference of the
Metabolomics Society

WEBINARS AND IN PERSON COURSES

EBI TRAINING

EMBL-EBI Training > Search EMBL-EBI Training

Search EMBL-EBI Training

Delivering world-class training in data-driven life sciences.

Search our courses, webinars and online tutorials

metabolomics × **Search**

Refine your search

On-demand training (7)

Type

Recorded webinar (1)

Online tutorial (6)

Duration

Less than 1 hour (2)

1 to 3 hours (5)

Live training (4)

Type

Webinar (1)

Virtual course (2)

Course at EMBL-EBI (1)

Status

Open (1)

Closed (3)

Year

2021 (2)

2020 (1)

2019 (1)

Location

Search results for metabolomics

Showing 1 - 10 out of 10 results in all training

COURSE AT EMBL-EBI
[Introduction to metabolomics analysis](#)
 This course will provide an introduction to **metabolomics** data analysis using publicly available software and tools. Participants will become familiar with the current state of experimental design,...

Closed: Materials available | 📅 05 - 08 Feb 2019 | 📍 European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), United Kingdom

ONLINE TUTORIAL
[Metabolomics: An introduction](#)
 This course provides a basic introduction into the rapidly emerging field of **metabolomics** and its importance and applications.

ONLINE TUTORIAL
[PhenoMeNal Gateway: Metabolomics data analysis in the cloud](#)
 The PhenoMeNal Gateway is the portal to your own PhenoMeNal Cloud Research Environment (CRE) containing an array of essential **metabolomics** applications. This course will give you an overview...

ONLINE TUTORIAL
[MetaboLights: Quick tour](#)
 This quick tour provides a brief introduction to EMBL-EBI's database for **Metabolomics** experiments and derived information,

VIRTUAL COURSE
[EMBL-EBI workshop: University of Pavia, 2021 \(Virtual\)](#)

Data resources at EMBL-EBI

Chemicals, molecules and drug discovery

ChEBI
ChEMBL
MetaboLights
Open Targets
SureChEMBL

Genes, genomes and RNA

ArrayExpress
Ensembl
European Nucleotide Archive
Expression Atlas
HGNC
MGnify
Rfam
RNACentral
VectorBase
WormBase

Proteins

AlphaFold DB
Enzyme Portal
InterPro
PDBe
Pfam
PRIDE
UniProt

Imaging and cellular structure

BioImage Archive
Electron Microscopy Data Bank
EMPIAR

Genetic variation and disease data

COVID-19 Data Platform
European Genome-phenome Archive
European Variation Archive
Mouse informatics

Literature and knowledge management

BioModels
BioSamples
BioStudies
Complex Portal
Europe PMC
GWAS Catalog
IntAct
OmicsDI
Ontologies
Reactome

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and Innovation

EMBL

NIH

Funded by
the European Union

*The Metabolomics team's activities were supported
in the past year by the above funding bodies*

Welcome Feedback

User input on existing and new features

- Any features you would like to see included?
- How to best capture assay and metabolite annotations?
- What other kind of data would you like us to capture?
- What interactions with other resources would you like to see?

Email us metabolights-help@ebi.ac.uk